

Testing a single fundamental principle yielding general relativity, particle physics, and gauge anomaly cancellation

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Abstract

The Lagrangians of general relativity and of the standard model of particle physics with massive neutrinos can be deduced from a single fundamental principle based on fluctuating strands of Planck radius. The approach yields unique and running values for the elementary particle masses and coupling constants that are predicted to agree with experiments when calculated with more effort. The fundamental principle also explains the principle of least action, the equality of inertial and gravitational mass, as well as the equality of the proton and the positron charge. The lack of new observable effects of relativistic quantum gravity is predicted.

Keywords: fundamental principle; general relativity; standard model with massive neutrinos; principle of least action; equivalence principle; gauge anomaly cancellation.

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1 From physics in nine lines to unification

To achieve a unified description of motion, it is most useful to start with the simplest description available. At present, nine short lines yield a compact and precise description that is in complete agreement with all observations and measurements about motion. Eight of the nine lines are built on the concept of Lagrangian L .

Line I: $\delta W = 0$

For every system, action $W = \int L dt$ is minimized in local motion [1, 2].

Line II: $v \leq c$

System speed v is limited by the speed of light c . This invariant [3] *implies* and *deduces* special relativity and, together with line I, restricts the possible Lagrangians [1].

Line III: $F \leq c^4/4G$

Force F is limited by c and by the gravitational constant G . This invariant [4] *implies* and *deduces* general relativity and, together with lines I and II, *fixes* the Hilbert Lagrangian and Einstein's field equations of general relativity, as proven in references [5–10] and as told in Appendix B.

Line IV: $W \geq \hbar$

Action W is limited by the quantum of action \hbar . This invariant [11–14] *implies* and *deduces* quantum theory [15–23] and restricts the possible Lagrangians.

Line V: $S \geq k \ln 2$

System entropy S is limited by $\ln 2$ times the Boltzmann constant k . This invariant *implies* and *deduces* the laws of thermodynamics, as proven in references [24, 25].

Line VI: $U(1)$

The Lie group $U(1)$ is the local gauge group of the electromagnetic interaction. When combined with lines I, II, and IV, this local Lie group *implies* and *deduces* the corresponding Lagrangian [26, 27].

Line VII: $SU(3)$ and broken $SU(2)$

These Lie groups are the local gauge groups of the two nuclear interactions. When com-

bined with lines I, II, and IV, these local Lie groups *imply* and *deduce* the corresponding Lagrangians [27].

Line VIII: 18 elementary particles

Everything that moves is made of 6 quarks, 6 leptons, the photon, the gluon, the W, the Z, the Higgs boson, and the undetected graviton – with all their quantum numbers. Together with the lines I, II, IV, VI, and VII, the elementary particles *fix* all algebraic terms in the standard model Lagrangian with massive neutrinos [27].

Line IX: 27 dimensionless constants of nature

The 3 coupling constants, the 14 remaining ratios of elementary particle masses to the Planck mass, the 8 mixing constants, the number of spatial dimensions, and the cosmological constant multiplied by the minimum area $4G\hbar/c^3$, together with the previous lines, *completely determine* the two Lagrangians. These dimensionless constants, 25 of which run with four-momentum, describe all observations about particles, space, and black holes, including all colors in nature [27].

The nine lines allow deducing all of fundamental physics. The nine lines suggest that nature is *simple* and that *little mathematics* is needed to describe its foundations – in contrast to the involved calculations necessary in quantum field theory and general relativity. The simplicity of the nine lines is one aspect of nature’s fascination.

Since 1973, despite all efforts, no deviation between measurements and the nine lines has been confirmed [9, 27]. In particular, elementary dark matter has not been detected [27]. Recent research suggests that dark matter might not be necessary to explain galaxy rotation curves [28]. Furthermore, it may be that dark energy is an effect of our specific location in the universe [29, 30] and thus that the cosmological constant is zero.

Because, so far, no test has found a confirmed deviation from the nine lines nor an observation not described by them, the nine lines provide the *foundation* for the following arguments. For the same reason, a unified theory is *unlikely* to predict new effects.

Because lines VI to IX appear *arbitrary*, the set of nine lines is not unified. To achieve unification, all nine lines must be shown to derive from *one* fundamental principle. This aim defines and specifies the challenge of unification. In Section 2 and Section 3, the *limit lines* II, III, IV, and V and their agreement with observations will be used to extract the common constituents of nature and to deduce a single fundamental principle. In the subsequent sections, the fundamental principle is argued to imply the remaining lines describing physics, and in particular, to imply the Lagrangian of the standard model with massive neutrinos. The fundamental principle is used to solve several open issues of particle physics. For completeness, the appendices clarify how the fundamental principle, together with the limit lines contained in it, implies the properties of black holes, thermodynamics, general relativity, and relativistic quantum theory. A disappointing prediction will arise: the lack of new observable effects due to the unified description of nature.

2 From the limit lines to strands

The *limit lines* II, III, IV, and V imply the impossibility of observing and defining trans-Planckian quantities and observables. Combining lines II, III, and IV yields the existence of a *minimum length* $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^3}$, twice the Planck length, and a corresponding *minimum area* [31–41]. The minimum length and time values, which are also the minimum *measurement errors* prevent the observation of any trans-Planckian effect, including any effect

below the minimum values. The minimum measurement errors further prevent the observation of any contradiction between general relativity and particle physics. The minimum measurement errors also imply that nature is *fuzzy* at the Planck scale. Therefore, the minimum errors prevent the definition of *derivatives* at the Planck scale. But derivatives are part of every Lagrangian and of every evolution equation. Every unified description of nature must also be valid at the Planck scale. The minimum measurement errors in nature thus *prevent* the existence of unified equations of motion and of unified Lagrangians. This result explains the lack of successful unification approaches in the past.

The minimum measurement errors also prevent *reaching* any Planck-scale limit that is defined with *all three* quantities c , \hbar , and G . This contrasts with Planck limits containing just one or two of these constants, which *can* be reached. Therefore, equations of motion are possible in relativistic quantum theory and in general relativity, but not in relativistic quantum gravity. In particular, the minimum measurement errors prevent the observation of any constituent in nature having minimum size.

The limit lines II, III, IV, and V also imply how unification has to proceed. The simplest derivation starts with black holes. The limit lines, together with the properties of horizons, imply that *black holes have an entropy* of the order of the Bekenstein-Hawking expression. It is derived in Appendix A. The existence of this black hole entropy implies that black holes are made of *fluctuating* constituents. The surface dependence of black hole entropy implies that the constituents are *filiform* [42–47]. The surface dependence of black hole entropy further implies that the constituents are *without branches, without a finite length, without ends, without knots, and open*, thus *extending to the cosmological horizon* [48, 49]. because all alternatives would yield different entropy dependencies.

The order of magnitude of black hole entropy implies that the fluctuating filiform constituents of black holes and horizons have a projected cross-section given by the minimum area, four times the Planck area. Because of the minimum measurement errors, the constituents of black holes are therefore *unobservable*. They are called *strands* in the following. To reproduce black hole entropy in its surface dependence and magnitude, horizons must be fluctuating *weaves* of strands with Planck radius [48–51], as presented in Appendix A.

Because every black hole can be seen either as a specific configuration of curved space or as a system of dense particles, they share the same degrees of freedom. Thus, *black holes, empty space, and particles are made of unobservable fluctuating strands with Planck radius*. The ‘strands’ are as unobservable as the hitherto used ‘points’.

The limit lines II, III, IV, and V allow deducing additional details. Matter is observed to consist of elementary fermions. Observations *distinguish* elementary fermion rotations by one turn from those by two turns, and likewise, simple exchanges of two fermions from double exchanges. Furthermore, elementary fermions are observed to be smaller than their Compton wavelength. Because of the limit lines and in contrast to the rotation of a ball or a planet, rotations of elementary fermions *cannot* be detected by following the motion of their geometric structure, shape, or surface features. In addition, due to the limit lines, *partial* rotations of elementary fermions are unobservable.

The limit lines II, III, IV, and V include the observations that elementary fermions of *different* masses, wave functions, and chiralities are observed to have the *same* spin value $\hbar/2$. Therefore, in contrast to the rotation of a ball or a planet, the spin of fermions cannot be a geometric effect but must be a *topological* effect.

Because of the limit lines, *the effects of full rotations of elementary fermions are not*

Dirac's trick: under rotation, tethered structures behave as spin $\hbar/2$ particles

The fermion trick: under exchange, tethered structures behave as fermions

Figure 1 Top: *Dirac's trick* proves that a non-trivial *tangle core* with three or more tethers behaves as a *spin $\hbar/2$ particle*: tether deformations return to the original state only after a double core rotation. A tethered fluctuating tangle core thus can *rotate indefinitely*. Bottom: The *fermion trick* proves that non-trivial tangle cores made of two or more strands behave as *fermions*: tether deformations return to the original state only after a double core exchange. Tethered fluctuating tangle cores thus can *orbit each other indefinitely*. Animated versions of the two tricks are available at vimeo.com/62228139 and vimeo.com/62143283, or at motionmountain.net/videos.html#strands.

only topological but are also always relative to the cosmological horizon, i.e., to the night sky. Fermions are thus topologically *related* to the cosmological horizon and thus topologically *connected* to it. The only remaining topological way to distinguish one from two elementary fermion rotations is by counting full rotations with respect to a distant environment using *Dirac's trick* and by following fermion exchange using the related *fermion trick* illustrated in Figure 1.

Already in 1929, Dirac showed in his lectures that spin $\hbar/2$ can only be described using *tethers*, i.e., using connections to distant fixed locations [52, 53]. *Dirac's trick* shows that crossing switches are the *only* changes that distinguish an unrotated fermion from a fermion rotated by 2π or exchanged fermions from unexchanged ones. The description confirms that a crossing switch is related to the quantum of action \hbar , as Kauffman stated [54, 55]. Fermions are thus connected to the cosmological horizon by unobservable strands. Because *fermions* have spin and can be counted, fermions are *tangles* of fluctuating strands with Planck radius.

The consequences of strands as *fermion* constituents can be checked. Constituents that have a larger radius than the Planck length would be observable, thus would yield observable wave functions and yield unhidden variables. Constituents that are not filiform or that have ends would neither yield fermion spin nor the wave behavior of quantum particles, as argued in Appendix C. Constituents that are not fluctuating would not yield probabilities in quantum measurements. Constituents that cannot tangle up would not yield quantum numbers, localizable particles, or entanglement [56, 57]. Constituents that do not form unknotted, *rational 3D tangles*, but have ends, branches, or knots, would not yield fermion behavior, antiparticles, virtual particles, and interactions. (For example, knots and mirror knots do not annihilate, whereas tangles and mirror tangles do.) More precisely, particles must be *rotating* rational 3D tangles of strands, thus rotating *3D braids* tethered to the cosmological horizon. Conversely, rotating particle tangles are fluctuating skeletons of wave functions, as argued in Appendix C. Constituents that do not form rotating tangles cannot yield wave functions as *oriented crossing densities* of particle tangles. To reproduce particles and quantum theory, particles must be fluctuating rational 3D *tangles* of strands of Planck radius.

The consequences of strands as constituents of *physical space* can be checked. Because physical space has three dimensions, can curve, is empty, has no preferred directions, is unique, behaves causally [58], and contains virtual particles, 'empty' physical space must be made of unobservable fluctuating filiform constituents with Planck radius that are untangled, but that can tangle. Constituents that are thinner are unphysical, whereas thicker ones would be observable and would not yield emptiness. Constituents that do not fluctuate would yield preferred directions. Constituents that are not filiform would not yield geodesics and curvature. Constituents that are unable to tangle up would not yield three spatial dimensions, nor yield virtual particles, nor yield causality. Constituents with branches or with ends would not yield the entropy of curved space. The constituents of physical space are *strands* and to realize all the observed properties, flat physical space must be an *aggregate of untangled strands*. Here, 'untangled' means that no pair of strands is braided. This yields

Definition 1: A *strand* is a tube of Planck radius around a one-dimensional smooth line in background space. Strands have no ends, no knots, and no branches. Strands cannot be cut and cannot intersect, but *can change* shape and length when other strands displace them, without any resistance to stretching, bending, or torsion.

Figure 2 Nature consists of fluctuating unobservable strands of Planck radius extending to the cosmological horizon. Aggregates of unentangled strands are observable and produce flat (a) and curved (b) three-dimensional empty space. Weaves of strands are observable and form black hole horizons (c). Rotating rational tangles of strands are observable and form particles and their probability densities (d). Even though the strands themselves are unobservable, all observations and all observables arise at skew strand crossings: every crossing switch produces an action \hbar . Physical existence is the production of crossing switches.

Definition 2: *Background space*, a three-dimensional *mathematical space*, is introduced by measurement apparatuses or by observers to describe strands and their fluctuations. Background space consists of points, has 3 dimensions, and is used in the illustrations in this article. Background space is *unavoidable* to describe nature and, in particular, is *unavoidable* to describe the emergence of physical space and of wave functions. Background space arises by averaging fluctuating strands and by extrapolating this average to small distances, to large distances, and to regions where physical space is undefined, such as behind horizons.

Definition 3: *Empty space*, or *physical space*, can be flat or curved. Its geodesics arise by *averaging the strand shapes* of strands that fluctuate in background space.

It will appear that *only* fluctuating unobservable strands with Planck radius reproduce two-dimensional horizons and black hole thermodynamics [48, 49], *and* reproduce localized fermions of spin $\hbar/2$, *and* reproduce the three dimensions of space. So far, no loophole has been found in the arguments for the *necessity* of strands. Any loophole

The *fundamental principle* of the strand tangle model

Figure 3 A *strand crossing switch* – keeping fixed the midpoint of the shortest distance between two non-parallel strand segments and rotating the attached segments on one side by 2π – specifies an event, the simplest observable process in nature; it defines \hbar as the unit of the physical action W . The most rapid observable crossing switch determines the double Planck time. Crossing switches of tangles determine probability densities and gauge field intensities. Crossing switches yield *unambiguous* predictions that can be tested in every experiment about motion. The fundamental principle, with its non-locality, non-commutativity, strand shape fluctuations, and background space, describes all known observations. The fundamental principle provides a *tiny theory of motion*.

that cannot be overcome would invalidate the strand tangle model. To avoid premature conclusions, the search for loopholes should continue.

The minimum measurement errors have an unintended consequence. Because strands have the minimum diameter, the measurement errors prevent the observations of single strands. Therefore, the minimum measurement errors also prevent the derivation and the existence of equations of motion for strands. In other words, the limit lines II, III, IV, and V *exclude* a mathematical description of strand dynamics. This disappointing result is the main reason that strands will take a long time to be accepted.

In total, it appears that particles, space, and horizons can be described as an agglomerate of fluctuating unobservable *strands* of Planck radius that constantly push onto each other. Nature thus resembles a heap of invisible, trembling, extremely thin, but uncuttable *spaghetti* without ends and without resistance to changes in length, shape, or torsion. An overview of how strands yield the systems observed in nature is given in Figure 2. Any observed deviation from this description would falsify the following arguments. The remaining step, leading from unobservable strands to physical observables, is provided by the fundamental principle.

3 From strands to the fundamental principle

Elementary particles are localized disturbances in empty space. As just argued, empty space consists of unobservable fluctuating strands of Planck radius without ends that cannot intersect or be cut. Because knots cannot form through fluctuations of such constituents, the only localized disturbances in empty space that yield particle properties are *tangles* of strands. Indeed, rotating tangle cores tethered to the cosmological horizon lead to spin and statistics, as Dirac showed in 1929 [52]. Rotating particles generate crossings and crossing switches of strands.

Definition 4: A skew strand *crossing* between two strand segments that are not coplanar and not intersecting is defined by the *shortest distance*, its orientation, and its *midpoint*.

Examples of crossing switches in nature

Figure 4 Crossing switches – shown by dotted circles – occur continuously in rotating tethered quantum particles. As shown in Figure 1, tether rearrangements allow particle rotation to continue forever.

Definition 5: A *crossing switch* is the twist-induced strand deformation that keeps the *midpoint* of a crossing *fixed* but rotates its orientation and the attached segments on one side by 2π , as illustrated in Figure 3.

Crossing switches can only occur at crossings, as illustrated in Figure 4 for rotating particles. Appendix C illustrates the notion of shortest distance, of its orientation, and of its midpoint. By definition, crossing switches are observer-invariant and thus are Lorentz-invariant processes. Because crossing switches are the only effects of particle rotation and of particle exchange, as illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 4, and because particle rotation and particle exchange are observable and described by \hbar , one is led to the conclusion, first drawn by Kauffman in 1987 [54, 55], that crossing switches of strands are *observable* and define Planck’s quantum of action \hbar :

Fundamental principle: The crossing switch, illustrated in Figure 3, *defines* Planck’s quantum of action \hbar and the Boltzmann constant k . The fastest possible crossing switch defines the Planck time. In nature, *each* crossing switch *generates* an action quantum \hbar .

With this fundamental principle, observable crossing switches of unobservable strands in particle tangles lead to all observation of *particle physics*, including quantum theory and quantum field theory, as explored in references [50, 51, 59–61] and as summarized below. In particular, the crossing switch density of a rotating fluctuating tangle core is the probability density, as argued in Appendix C. Crossing switches also play a role in empty space and in black holes.

Empty space implies that strands and their fluctuations are unobservable. Thus, the observation of Planck-scale fluctuations of empty space is impossible. The emptiness and isotropy of physical space also imply the lack of permanent topological structures. The transient, short-lived topological structures arising through fluctuations are virtual particles. Average strand shapes determine geodesics and spatial curvature. Locations and events in physical or mathematical space result from crossing switches. Observable crossing switches of unobservable strands lead to all observable aspects of flat and curved space [48, 49]. Because crossing switches imply virtual particles and because virtual particles obey the uncertainty relation, it makes sense to associate crossing switches with Planck’s quantum of action \hbar .

Black hole entropy arises through the fluctuating weaves that strands can form at a horizon, as shown in detail in references [48–51]. The different weaves are distinguished by the different signs of their strand crossings. Observable crossing switches of unobservable strands lead to all observable aspects of black holes [48, 49]. Because crossing

Crossing switches couple to photons

Figure 5 A crossing switch intrinsically couples to a twist and thus to photons. (The model for the photon is deduced later on.) Because of this coupling, each crossing switch is *observable*, even though the strands themselves are not. The intrinsic coupling of crossing switches to photons enables observations, measurements, and unambiguous predictions. The coupling implies that in every case of motion, strand fluctuations select those deformations that minimize the number of crossing switches. This is the *principle of least action*. As explained later on, the coupling also determines the fine-structure constant.

switches imply the entropy, mass, and temperature of black holes, with their exact values, it makes sense to associate crossing switches with Planck’s quantum of action \hbar . Despite the tethering, black holes can rotate using Dirac’s trick.

In the three cases of particles, empty space, and black holes, each crossing switch is a change described by Planck’s quantum of action \hbar . The relation between topology and \hbar is the essence of the fundamental principle. So far, this definition of \hbar appears to be the only possible answer to Wheeler’s question “How come the quantum?” [62], despite many intense attempts [63–70]. Finding another answer would invalidate the strand model.

In short, the limit lines II, III, IV, and V were used to deduce the fundamental principle that associates Planck’s quantum of action \hbar to a crossing switch. Insofar as the arguments leading to the fundamental principle appear to exclude all alternatives, the description of nature with strands is unique. Appendix C contains further arguments for the uniqueness of the description of quantum theory with strands. As argued in the following sections, the fundamental principle can be used to derive the remaining lines I, VI, VII, VIII, and IX. As a consequence, the fundamental principle will be shown to describe all observations in physics and to be unique. Any observed deviation from the nine lines or any alternative, inequivalent description would falsify the strand model.

4 From the fundamental principle to the principle of least action

All motion in nature, in general relativity and in quantum field theory, follows the principle of least action. For sufficiently short times, action is always *minimized* [2]. Because the quantum of action is the measurement unit of action, and because the value of action is independent of the observer [15], one can state that nature keeps the number of action quanta as small as possible. For strands, this implies that the principle of least action is the principle of the *fewest crossing switches*.

In nature, all measurement apparatuses and all observations use electromagnetic effects. Also all SI measurement units are defined with electromagnetic effects. Electromagnetic fields are moving and rotating twists in single strands, as shown in Section 5 using Reidemeister’s theorem. The three-dimensional geometry of crossing switches im-

plies that all crossing switches *couple* to photons, as illustrated in Figure 5. The coupling implies that crossing switches are *observable*, even though the strands themselves are not. The coupling thus *explains* the fundamental principle. Figure 5 also implies that all observations and measurements are *electromagnetic* and are *quantum*. All experiments confirm this statement. Because in electromagnetic fields, wavelength and period are related, Figure 5 also implies that all electromagnetic fields have periods longer than twice the Planck time $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^5}$.

Because crossing switches couple to the electromagnetic field, in each physical system, among all possible strand fluctuations, nature will choose those strand fluctuations that require the smallest coupling, the smallest effort, and thus the smallest change. As a consequence, nature *minimizes* the number of crossing switches. In other words, nature chooses those fluctuations that yield the smallest action. Strands and their fundamental principle thus *derive* the principle of least action.

Strands thus derive line I of the introduction from the fundamental principle. A literature search did not find another derivation of the principle of minimum action, ab initio or from \hbar . The literature does not even contain *attempts* to derive the principle of least action or a discussion of the feasibility of such attempts. Any observed deviation or any inequivalent derivation of the principle of least action would falsify the strand model.

As a side result, strands confirm that a unified description of nature *cannot* be based on a unified Lagrangian, not only because such a Lagrangian would be based on continuous fields and continuous space, which contradict lines II to V of the introduction, but also because the origin of such fields would have to be assumed and not be derived. Specifically, any Lagrangian claiming to be unified either explicitly includes assumptions that contain lines VI to IX of the introduction, or includes assumptions similar to or equivalent to them, without deriving them ab initio. As a result, no Lagrangian can be unified.

5 From the fundamental principle to interactions, bosons, and couplings

In nature, interactions influence the *phase* of particles. In Appendix C, the illustration of the phase implies that tangle deformations change the phase of particles. Therefore, in the strand tangle model, *interactions* are processes that *deform* particle tangles. Surprisingly, the possible tangle deformations that change crossings can be *classified*. Reidemeister achieved the complete classification in 1926 [71]. His theorem proves that all tangle deformations with topological effects are composed of *three* so-called *Reidemeister moves*: twist, pokes and slides. The moves rotate strand segments and are illustrated in Figure 6.

Reidemeister's theorem applies to knots, to links, and to tangles. The Reidemeister moves classify all deformations that change crossings. In the strand tangle model, this implies that the Reidemeister moves classify all strand deformations that lead to observable effects.

Each Reidemeister move naturally generates a Lie gauge group [61]. For *twists*, the first Reidemeister moves, the top row of Figure 7 proves that the concatenation of two twists by π yields the same effect as no twist at all. Generalizing twists to rotations of the dotted circle region by *arbitrary* rotation angles yields the complete, continuous, local Lie group U(1) and specifies photons [50, 51, 61]. Defining the angle of a twist leads to a corresponding local freedom of gauge, and implies Maxwell's equations, as told in reference [59]. In particular, because strands reproduce quantum electrodynamics at all scales above the Planck scale, no measurable deviations from QED or from the electron

Figure 6 The strand tangle model of the gauge interactions is based on the mathematical theorem that the three Reidemeister moves *classify* all deformations of topological structures with crossing changes [71]. Each Reidemeister move shifts and rotates the strand region enclosed by a dotted circle by an angle π . Each Reidemeister move determines an observed gauge group and a gauge boson tangle, as told in the text.

g-factor arise [59].

For *pokes*, the second Reidemeister moves, the behavior of the dotted circles in Figure 7 shows that their concatenation leads to the following multiplication table:

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc}
 \cdot & \tau_x & \tau_y & \tau_z \\
 \tau_x & -1 & i\tau_z & -i\tau_y \\
 \tau_y & -i\tau_z & -1 & i\tau_x \\
 \tau_z & i\tau_y & -i\tau_x & -1
 \end{array} \quad (1)$$

An entry -1 means that the dotted circle has rotated by 2π and its strands are tangled. The table shows that the operators τ_x , τ_y and τ_z behave like i times the Pauli matrices:

$$\tau_x = i\sigma_x = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tau_y = i\sigma_y = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tau_z = i\sigma_z = i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Pokes, local rotations by angle π , thus generate the algebra of SU(2) and behave like the unit quaternions. Pokes thus model the unbroken weak bosons. Generalizing pokes to *arbitrary* local rotation angles yields the complete, continuous Lie group SU(2) [61]. In

Twists, or **first Reidemeister moves**, are related to a crossing switch in a single strand. In a tangle core, twists on a single strand around a given axis yields a $U(1)$ Lie group.

Pokes, or **second Reidemeister moves**, on pairs of strand segments generate an $SU(2)$ Lie algebra, because the three orthogonal rotations by π reproduce the belt trick:

Slides, or **third Reidemeister moves**, acting on segment pairs in trivial three-strand tangles, can be generalized to the generators of the Lie group $SU(3)$:

Figure 7 The three Reidemeister moves – twists, pokes, and slides – rotate the dotted circles by π . They yield the behavior of $U(1)$ and the algebras of $SU(2)$ and $SU(3)$. Generalizing the deformations to arbitrary angles yields the full Lie groups (before symmetry breaking) that are observed in nature.

the strand tangle model, to each deformation there is also a corresponding freedom of gauge. This freedom yields the (unbroken) local SU(2) invariance of the standard model. As explained elsewhere [50, 51], also the breaking of the SU(2) gauge symmetry arises and maximal parity violation occurs, because tangles rotating in opposite directions, due to the chirality of their cores, naturally couple in different ways to weak bosons [61]. Strands also reproduce the Higgs mechanism, because the Higgs boson adds a vacuum strand to the unbroken weak bosons, thus generating mass and, for the W, electric charge. No measurable deviations from the theory of the weak interaction arise.

Slides, the third Reidemeister moves, yield the deformations illustrated in the lower part of Figure 7. Like for pokes, the diagrams for slides are local rotations by π and allow deducing the matrix representations for the Hermitian slide operators λ_1 to λ_{10} [61]. In each row, the first three diagrams form a SU(2) subgroup.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_3 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \lambda_4 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_5 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_9 &= \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \lambda_6 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_7 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_{10} &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, & \lambda_8 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

The matrix representation proves that the set of eight slide generators $i\lambda_1, \dots, i\lambda_8$ forms the Lie algebra of SU(3) [61], the so-called Gell-Mann representation. These eight operators fulfill the trace relations $\text{tr} \lambda_n = 0$ and $\text{tr}(\lambda_n \lambda_m) = 2\delta_{nm}$. The multiplication table of the slide generators can either be deduced from the matrix representation or be read off directly from the strand diagrams in Figure 7 [50, 51, 61]. The operators λ_9 and λ_{10} are provided in the table and the figure to show the three SU(2) subgroups. The three operators λ_3 , λ_9 , and λ_{10} form a two-dimensional linear space and are traditionally replaced by λ_3 and λ_8 . The set $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_8$ forms a *basis* of the Lie algebra of SU(3). Generalizing slides from rotations by π to rotations by *arbitrary* angles yields the complete, continuous, local Lie group SU(3) [61]. Again, the SU(3) group defines a local freedom of gauge. This local gauge symmetry yields the Lagrangian of the strong interaction. Slides thus define eight gluons, reproduce their “double” color charge, spin 1, negative P parity, vanishing mass, and vanishing electric charge, exclude CP violation of the strong interaction, imply asymptotic freedom, yield the quark model of hadrons, and form glueballs, as told in detail elsewhere [60]. Because strands reproduce quantum chromodynamics at all scales above the Planck scale, no measurable deviations from QCD arise [60].

Each Reidemeister move thus defines the strand model of the respective gauge boson before symmetry breaking. The tangles of all elementary bosons are illustrated in Figure 8. All bosons are elongated structures. Unbroken gauge vector bosons are topologically *trivial* tangles; they cannot be localized by pulling their tethers. This yields spin 1, boson behavior, and vanishing mass.

Reidemeister’s theorem states that every deformation of a tangle that changes crossings is a combination of twists, pokes, and slides [71]. The theorem excludes other moves and

Elementary bosons are tangles of 1, 2 or 3 strands that follow a straight line at large distances:

Figure 8 The rational 3D tangles for all elementary bosons are illustrated. They consist of one, two, or three strands. All boson tangle cores *with spin* rotate during propagation. The *graviton* has spin 2 because its core can rotate by π and yield the original shape. The W, Z, and the Higgs are localizable, couple to the Higgs, and thus have mass. Only the W tangle core is topologically chiral, and therefore, the W is the only electrically charged elementary boson.

thus excludes other gauge groups and other gauge bosons. This is observed [27].

The strand tangle model of the *Higgs boson* is a braid with six crossings in three asymptotically parallel strands, as illustrated in Figure 8. The braid explains the vanishing spin and charge values, the positive C and P parity values, the coupling to the W, the Z, fermions, and to itself, and the decays [50, 51]. Strands imply that there is only one Higgs boson and that it is the only particle with the same quantum numbers as the vacuum.

Strands imply that the *graviton* is a twisted pair of asymptotically parallel strands [48, 49], as illustrated in Figure 8. Due to its rotation invariance after a core rotation by $\pi/2$, the strand tangle model yields spin 2. When the graviton tangle advances, its core rotates. Because the graviton tangle is also topologically trivial, it has vanishing mass and charge values. No additional elementary boson can consist of two strands or can have spin 2. No additional elementary boson can exist; this also excludes the inflaton and other conjectured bosons. Dirac's trick implies that virtual gravitons arise around every massive particle whenever it rotates. The geometry of the situation automatically yields a $1/r^2$ dependence of the virtual graviton density around a massive particle. In other words,

The *geometry* of the Feynman diagram for the absorption of a photon by an electron

Figure 9 The average shapes for a photon approaching an electron describe the electron phase change and visualize the interaction vertex of quantum electrodynamics. This is the 3D description of a ‘quantum jump’. The geometry allows estimating the fine-structure constant numerically, as explained in the text.

Dirac’s trick explains the inverse square law of gravity. Particle tethers thus define both graviton density and spin density. In contrast, particle cores define wave functions and charge density. And because a rotation by 4π of a particle is equivalent to no rotation, strands visualize why Einstein-Cartan theory and twisters play no role in nature.

As told in line IX of the introduction, nature is also characterized by specific *constants*. The most well-known are the three gauge coupling constants. Because of the description of interactions as tangle deformations, the coupling constants are *unique* and are determined by the *average geometric shape* of tangles. The values of the coupling constants are determined by the fluctuation statistics of charged fermion and charged boson tangles described by the processes on the right of Figure 6, as told in references [59, 60]. So far, no expression for the ropelength of a knot has been found; the same is valid for the coupling constants.

The details of the electron-photon interaction are illustrated in Figure 9. This figure allows a simple estimate of the *fine-structure constant*. As the figure illustrates, the average angle between the three outer tether crossings of an electron tangle is a right angle, so that $\bar{\delta} = \pi/2$. Such a chiral outer tether pair absorbs only photon cores approaching within the cone spanned by the two tethers. The average *solid angle* of the cone is $\Omega = 4\pi \sin^2 \pi/8$. Compared to the full solid angle 4π , this is a fraction $(2 - \sqrt{2})/4$. Each of the *three* cones will absorb *half* of the arriving photons, because only half of them have the correct helicity. The average absorption probability over all incoming photon directions inside each cone is estimated to lead to a further factor of $1/2$. At low energy, a charged electron is thus expected to absorb a fraction

$$1/\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{strands}}} \approx (3/4)(2 - \sqrt{2})/4 \approx 0.11 \quad (4)$$

of all incoming photons. For comparison, the experimental value is

$$1/\sqrt{\alpha_{\text{exp}}} \approx 0.0854 \quad (5)$$

This simple strand estimate is thus about 30% too large. A slightly better estimate was deduced in reference [59] using numerical calculations. Efforts to achieve higher precision are ongoing.

At high energy, because of relativistic effects, the average spatial tether distribution and thus the average shape of tangle cores are *flattened*. Therefore, the strand tangle model implies that all particle properties that depend on the average core shape *run* with energy. These *geometric* properties include masses, mixing constants, and couplings. In contrast, strands predict that the *topological* particle properties, such as particle quantum numbers, do *not* run with energy. Both consequences agree with observations. Because no other quantities depend on average tangle shapes, strands predict the lack of further quantum gravity effects.

Strands allow estimating the fine-structure constant at the Planck energy, when the electron tangle is flattened completely. In this case, the three chiral tether pairs cover half the full flat angle 2π . Dividing by 4, because of the two helicities and of the angular average inside each tether pair, implies an estimated value 0.125 for $1/\sqrt{\alpha(\text{Pl})}$ at Planck energy. The value for the standard model, deduced from reference [72], is about 0.1. Again, the simple strand estimate is too high. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that strands qualitatively reproduce the observed increase of the fine-structure constant with energy. More precise estimates for the running are a topic of research.

The geometry of the strong interaction also yields an estimate for the *strong coupling constant*. Using the average geometry of the gluon and quark tangles, reference [60] deduced an estimate for the strong coupling constant at Planck energy. The estimate deviates from the standard model extrapolation [72] by 15%. Again, due to the relativistic shape change of tangle cores, strands predict the running of the strong coupling constant. At low energy, quark tangles remain topologically interlocked and lead to a quark interaction potential that increases linearly with distance [60]. All this is observed [27].

Strands thus confirm line II and derive line VI, line VII, and part of line IX of the introduction from Reidemeister's theorem. The literature does not appear to contain any other *ab initio* derivation – i.e., any other derivation from the Planck scale or any other derivation from a single principle – of the gauge interactions and their quantum field theories, *or* of the elementary bosons, *or* of the universal law of gravitation, *or* of the coupling constants and their running. Any observed deviation or any inequivalent derivation of the mentioned lines would falsify the strand model.

6 From the fundamental principle to fermions, masses, and mixings

Because tangles with four or more strands have substructures that can rotate independently, tangles of *elementary* particles can consist of only one, two, or three strands. Tangles of four or more strands are thus *composed*. Elementary bosons are tangles whose tethers approach a straight line at large distances and thus realize integer spin and boson statistics. In contrast, fermions are tangles whose tethers depart in all three dimensions.

Elementary fermions realize Dirac's trick and the fermion trick of Figure 1 and thus have spin $\hbar/2$. Therefore, elementary fermions can only be non-trivial tangles of two or three strands. *Two* tangled strands form quarks, *three* tangled strands form leptons. All elementary fermion tangles, including neutrinos, are chiral, couple to the Higgs, are non-trivial, thus have mass, and therefore are Dirac particles. The Higgs boson braid yields a *classification* of non-trivial rational 3D tangles leading to three lepton and three quark generations [50, 51, 59, 60]. The classification of the fermion tangles also *excludes any* other additional elementary fermion, and thus excludes elementary dark matter.

Each fermion, like each massive particle, consists of an infinite series of tangles that

Quarks - 'tetrahedral' tangles made of two strands (only simplest family members)

Parity $P = +1$, Baryon number $B = +1/3$, Spin $S = 1/2$

Charge $Q = -1/3$

Charge $Q = +2/3$

Leptons - 'cubic' tangles made of three strands (only simplest family members)

Figure 10 The simplest tangles for all elementary fermions are shown. All elementary fermion tangles consist of two or three braided strands. Their non-trivial rotating rational 3D tangles yield spin $\hbar/2$ and fermion behavior. At large distances from the tangle core, the four tethers of a quark follow the axes of a tetrahedron, and the six tethers of a lepton follow the coordinate axes. All cores are localized, realize the belt trick, and thus yield unique positive mass values. The tangles of the quarks (once the Higgs is taken into account), the electron, muon, and tau are topologically chiral and thus electrically charged. Neutrino cores are twisted strand triplets: they are geometrically chiral but not topologically chiral; thus, they are electrically neutral. The additional tangles arising through the Higgs coupling, not shown here, explain the lack of further fermion generations [50, 51, 59, 60]. (Tangle improvements might be necessary.) Antiparticles are mirror tangles; they are not shown. Additional elementary fermions are excluded.

Figure 11 When leptons rotate, their six tethers perform a continuous sequence of Dirac tricks. The animation for an electron tangle, accessible at desmos.com/3D/46kkmamfwy, was produced by Ronwnor. The central triangle is the tangle core of an electron and determines its position, spatial distribution, chirality, and electric charge. The rotation determines spin, phase, and mass. The oriented crossing density due to strand fluctuations yields the wave function.

arise due to the coupling to one or more Higgs braids. The simplest elementary fermion tangles are given in Figure 10. The (rotating) tangles in the figure reproduce all *quantum numbers* of quarks and leptons, including spin, C parity, P parity, chirality, all charges, and flavor [60]. The charges are explored in more detail in the next section.

The strand tangle model of elementary particles also explains the origin of *mass*. An elementary particle with mass advances through the vacuum in the same way that a maple seed falls through the air: in both cases, propagation is coupled to rotation due to *shape chirality*. When an elementary particle with mass advances through the vacuum, its chiral tangle core rotates. The faster the core rotates, the higher the mass. Because Dirac's trick produces inertial particle rotation and also produces virtual gravitons around a particle, as illustrated in Figure 1, inertial mass and gravitational mass are *identical* for all particles [48, 49]. Indeed, the equivalence principle is observed to hold to high precision [9].

In the same way that the rotation speed of a maple seed depends on the chiral shape of its wing, the rotation speed and thus the mass value of an elementary particle depend on the (average) chiral shape of its tangle core and on the motion of its tethers. The

mass values of antiparticles and particles are automatically equal. Generally speaking, among tangles with the same number of tethers, more complex tangles rotate faster and thus have higher mass. By comparing tangle complexities, the strand tangle model yields the correct mass sequences among leptons and quarks [59, 60]. In particular, because the tangle complexity increases with each generation, the strand tangle model predicts *normal mass ordering* for neutrinos. Using the same argument, strands also predict the correct mass sequence among the hadrons with the same number of tethers, as shown in reference [60]. These qualitative consequences of strands agree with observations.

The strand tangle model also yields first quantitative statements about the mass values of elementary particles. Figure 11 visualizes that the tethers of a rotating lepton follow a specific sequence of intermediate configurations. In each intermediate configuration, each of the six tethers must have the correct distribution of the $6!$ possible ones in space. For each of the two core rotations, three intermediate configurations are needed to specify Dirac's trick. These $2 \cdot 3$ intermediate configurations must occur in the correct sequence. The probability per time of Dirac's trick is thus at most

$$m_{\text{lepton-strands}} < \left(\frac{1}{6!}\right)^{2 \cdot 3} \approx 7.2 \times 10^{-18} \approx 44 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (6)$$

In this expression, the maximum possible elementary particle mass, $\sqrt{\hbar c/4G} = 0.61 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ GeV}/c^2$ or half the Planck mass, has been inserted as the mass unit. The calculated lepton mass value is an *upper limit* because the processes and time needed for the core rotation were neglected. Nevertheless, the expression is one of the first available *ab initio* estimates of a particle mass. Strands thus solve the *lepton mass hierarchy* problem: lepton masses are much smaller than (half) the Planck mass because of the low probability per time of Dirac's trick when their tangles advance through the vacuum. The low probability, together with the strand model for black holes, also implies that gravity is always intrinsically weaker than the gauge interactions, as expected [73]. One notes that the hierarchy problem is solved without additional interactions, additional dimensions, and additional particles. The literature offers no competing model with these properties.

The *measured* mass value of the most massive lepton, the tau, is

$$m_{\tau\text{-exp}} = 1.78(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (7)$$

The mass of the tau is thus about 25 times smaller than the upper lepton mass limit suggested by strands. This happens because, apart from the tethers, also the tau *core* must be set into rotational motion. This requirement further reduces the probability per time for the full tau rotation and leads to a mass value for the tau that is smaller than the lepton mass limit just estimated.

The muon and electron tangles are less complex than the tau tangle. Because their cores are simpler, as illustrated in Figure 10, they rotate less frequently when propagating through the vacuum, and thus their mass values are lower than that of the tau. Deriving mass estimates for each lepton and for each quark is a subject of research. Any disagreement between future strand mass calculations and the observed mass values would falsify the strand tangle model.

The strand tangle model also enables estimates of the Higgs boson mass. As shown in Figure 8, the Higgs boson tangle is a three-strand braid with six crossings. The braid topology explains the vanishing spin, the vanishing electric charge, and the positive C

and P parities – the same quantum numbers as empty space. The Higgs core advances through empty space *without* rotating. When the Higgs tangle of Figure 8 advances to the right, the last crossing on the left end is undone, and a new crossing between the same two strands is added on the right end. Then, this process of undoing and redoing also occurs for the two other strand pairs. Calculating the Higgs mass from the strand tangle model requires estimating the probability per time for this motion process. For a tether to go around another in a set of three, a total of four displacement steps with a length of one strand diameter are needed. In each step, the moving tether can move forward to the next step, move backward, or move away. This gives an estimated probability of at most $1/3^4$. The full cycle of six exchanges of tether pairs yields a probability per time of

$$m_{\text{Higgs-strands}} < \frac{1}{(6 \cdot 3^4)^6} \approx 7.6 \times 10^{-17} \approx 463 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (8)$$

The maximum elementary particle mass was again used as the mass unit. From the geometry of the situation, a minimum value for the probability of strand motion is $1/4^4$. The strand estimate for the Higgs mass then is

$$0.5 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{Higgs-strands}} < 463 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (9)$$

For such a back-of-the-envelope approach, a large range is unavoidable. The range includes the measured value

$$m_{\text{Higgs-exp}} = 125(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (10)$$

The strand estimate appears to be the first ab initio determination of the Higgs mass, contrasting those based on experimental data [74].

The strand tangle model also yields an estimate for the mass of the W boson. Figure 8 illustrates that the W boson tangle arises from the Higgs mechanism. The Higgs mechanism breaks the SU(2) symmetry by *braiding* an additional vacuum strand into the unbroken weak boson tangles and the nontrivial tangle thus acquires a non-zero mass value. The measured mass of the W boson is

$$m_{\text{W-exp}} = 80.4(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (11)$$

The rotation of the W tangle core is most easily imagined as a rotation around the line of sight when looking at the center of the W tangle core illustrated in Figure 8. For a W boson tangle moving towards the reader, the encountered vacuum strands put the core into rotation around the direction of motion. For a W core rotation, each crossing must move to the position and orientation of the next crossing. Each of the three crossings can move, for each of the three coordinates, in the correct direction or in the wrong one, and move, for each orientation, towards the correct orientation or the wrong one. The correct motion is thus at most 1 out of $4^3 = 64$ possible options. To realize the full core rotation, all three crossings must move three times into the correct position and orientation. The probability per time yields, again using the maximum elementary particle mass as the mass unit,

$$m_{\text{W-strands}} < \frac{1}{(64^3)^3} \approx 5.6 \times 10^{-17} \approx 339 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (12)$$

Given that the estimate $1/64$ could be too large by up to 30%, the strand estimate of the W boson mass is

$$32 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{W-strands}} < 339 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (13)$$

The estimate is rough but contains the measured value. The W mass estimate differs from the mass estimate for the electron, whose core is topologically similar, because, due to the different asymptotic tether geometry, the rotation of the W requires no Dirac trick.

The Z tangle of Figure 8 yields a similar mass range. Because it has 4 crossings and thus is more complex than the W , the Z mass is expected to be somewhat higher than the W mass. This is observed. Better estimates for all boson masses, for their running, and thus for the weak coupling constant are in work.

Strands explain fermion mixing as the braiding and unbraiding of particle tangles. Strands thus automatically imply that mixing – described by mixing angles and CP phases – is due to the weak interaction, will occur preferably between neighboring generations, and, for the second generation, preferably to the first. The fermion tangles in Figure 10 imply that the mixing among the generations will differ less among neutrinos, due to their low mass values and low mass differences, but will differ more among quarks. Strands imply that *mixing angles* and *CP phases* are determined by the average core shapes, which depend on length contraction and on time dilation, and thus will run with energy. All this is observed [27] or expected. As in the case of fermion masses, no expressions for the CMK or PMNS matrix elements arise. Numerical estimates for the matrix elements and their running are in work.

Strands thus *promise* to calculate all constants of nature. Finding closed expressions for knot shapes is one of the unsolved problems of mathematics. Only numerical calculations appear possible. Therefore, particle masses and their runnings are not available as closed expressions in the strand model. Despite the rough estimates given above, so far, only one alternative approach in the literature calculates all the values of the constants, namely the *octonion model* by Singh [75–77]. The octonion model has an involved mathematical foundation resting on a continuous space with higher dimensions that is combined with the algebra of octonions. As one consequence, in its present form, the octonion model predicts additional particles and interactions [78]. The octonion model is not based on a simple principle, but has the advantage of yielding precise estimates for the fundamental constants.

In total, the fundamental principle, together with the classification of simple rational tangles and the classification of tangle deformations, implies the particle spectrum, the interaction spectrum, fermion mixing, and every constant appearing in the standard model of particle physics with massive neutrinos. As presented elsewhere [50, 51, 59, 60], the tangle topologies of the allowed elementary particles also yield every observed interaction vertex and thus *every term* in the Lagrangian of particle physics. Because elementary particles consist of three strands or fewer, strands exclude any vertex with more than four particles, any additional interaction vertex, and thus any additional term in the Lagrangian. This exclusion ensures renormalization. Usual *local* quantum field theory with *point* particles follows in the limit $G \rightarrow 0$, i.e., for strands of zero radius. As required, the minimum length derives the constants that quantum field theory cannot derive. In addition, despite the existence of a minimum length, strands imply that no deviations from local quantum field theory are measurable. This agrees with all observations [27].

Strands thus derive line VIII of the introduction from tangle classification and promise to derive the constants in line IX, with their running, from the shapes of particle tangles. So far, the literature does not appear to contain any other derivation from a single principle of the spectrum of the elementary fermions, *or* of their masses and mixings, *or* of the equality of inertial and gravitational mass, thus of the equivalence principle,

or of the standard model Lagrangian with massive neutrinos. Strands exclude additional measurable effects of quantum gravity. As will be discussed in detail elsewhere, it appears that the cosmological constant due to strands is negligible, in disagreement with the mainstream, but in possible agreement with the latest theoretical and experimental results [29, 30] that also question the mainstream. Tests of this prediction require waiting for new experimental results. Any observed deviation or any inequivalent derivation of lines VIII and IX would falsify the strand model.

7 From the fundamental principle to gauge anomaly cancellation

Positrons and protons are observed to have the same electric charge. In the strand tangle model, electric charge is due to the *topological chirality* of the boson and fermion tangles illustrated in Figure 8 and Figure 10 because topological chirality – in contrast to geometric chirality – is the property that enables a tangle to absorb or emit photons [59].

In the strand tangle model of elementary particles, each chiral crossing corresponds to *one third* of an electric charge unit e . Positrons contain *three* chiral outer crossings of the *same* sign and thus have *one unit* of electric charge. The same argument holds for the W boson. The other elementary bosons are not topologically chiral and thus are electrically neutral. In contrast, quarks contain outer crossings of *different* signs. Their braid structure leads to either one or two outer crossings of the same sign. As a consequence, quarks have *fractional* electric charges of either $\pm e/3$ or $\pm 2e/3$. Because electric charge is due to topological chirality and not to geometric chirality, the fermion tangles explain the observed fractional electric charge of quarks, the integer charge of the charged leptons, and the vanishing electric charge of neutrinos [50, 51, 59, 60].

The strand tangle model also implies that quarks have *three* color charges that are a direct consequence of the tetrahedral structure of the quark tangles: when two quarks form a meson, three tethers of one quark interlink with three tethers of the other [60]. The three basic orientations yield the three colors. As a consequence of the three possible color charges, the strand tangle model, with the particle spectrum and the interaction spectrum it produces, implies that each fermion generation is free of gauge anomalies.

Strands thus derive the electric and the color charge quantum numbers contained in line VIII of the introduction from the topology of particle tangles. A literature search found no other ab initio derivation – i.e., any other derivation from the Planck scale or any other derivation from a single principle – of the electric and color charges of the observed elementary particles. A further literature search found no other ab initio derivation – i.e., any other derivation from the Planck scale or any other derivation from a single principle – of the equality of proton and positron electric charges and of the lack of gauge anomalies. Any observed deviation or any inequivalent derivation of these results would falsify the strand model.

8 Conclusion and outlook

In summary, nature is simple. *Particles* are tangles of unobservable strands, *space* consists of untangled unobservable strands, and *horizons* are weaves of unobservable strands. In particular, *Dirac's trick* for particle tangles implies spin, fermion behavior, de Broglie's relation, wave-particle duality, wave functions, Dirac's equation, Feynman's path inte-

grals, fermion masses, inverse square gravity, the equivalence principle, and black hole rotation.

In agreement with all observations and all experiments performed so far, nature is described by a

Tiny theory of motion: The single *fundamental principle* for strands of Planck radius, illustrated in Figure 3 and associating Planck’s quantum of action \hbar to crossing switches, implies the Lagrangians of general relativity and of the standard model of elementary particle physics with massive neutrinos, explains the observed interactions and the observed elementary particles, deduces their electric charges and their other quantum numbers, allows calculating their masses, coupling constants, and mixing constants, describes nature with complete accuracy, *excludes* any observation of ‘new physics’, and *rules out* any inequivalent unified description. The *only measurable, non-trivial effects* of quantum gravity appear to be the masses of the observed elementary particles, including neutrinos, the coupling constants, the mixing constants, and their running.

The tiny theory must be continuously tested and challenged about its agreement with observations, its underlying assumptions, its elimination of points, of unified equations, and of a unified Lagrangian, its exclusion of inequivalent approaches to unification, and its particle–tangle assignments. In particular, calculations of particle masses, coupling constants, and mixing constants need to be improved and compared to observations. Any observation deviating from the fundamental principle or any inequivalent alternative approach with the same explanatory power would invalidate the strand model.

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A From strands back to black holes and thermodynamics

The general connection between the surface dependence of black hole entropy and filiform constituents has been known since the 1990s [42–47]. As argued now, the disappearance of the factor $\ln 2$ from Bekenstein’s entropy bound and from black hole entropy is due to strands, the fundamental principle, and the built-in non-locality. In addition, strands derive several statements about observable properties of black holes.

In black hole horizons, strands form *weaves*. In contrast to everyday tissues, the weaves are fluctuating and irregular [48, 49]. In black hole horizons, strands leave the horizon and extend into the surrounding space, as illustrated in Figure 12. In the first approximation, strand crossings produce *two* possible states per minimum horizon area, because a crossing has two possible signs. However, now and then, neighboring strands also cross *above* each minimum area. The resulting average number of microstates per minimum area can be calculated [48, 49].

To calculate the probability of crossings per minimum area, one imagines the central crossing in Figure 12 surrounded by an infinite series of rings, each with a minimum area $4G\hbar/c^3$, that are numbered. The central crossing corresponds to $n = 0$. Ring number n

A black hole horizon in the strand tangle model

Cross-section:

Top view:

Figure 12 The strand tangle model of a black hole is illustrated. The horizon is a thin, spherical, and fuzzy region produced by the fluctuating crossing switches of tight strands with a Planck radius. (Strands radii are not drawn to scale.) Due to the crossings *above* the horizon, the number of microstates per minimum area is greater than 2, as explained in the text. Not all strands of the surrounding vacuum are shown.

encloses an area given by n times the minimum area. Now, the probability p_1 that a strand from ring 1 crosses above the central minimum area is

$$p_1 = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2!} . \quad (\text{A1})$$

The probability that a strand departing from ring n crosses above the central minimum area is

$$p_n = \frac{1}{n+1} p_{n-1} = \frac{1}{(n+1)!} , \text{ for } n > 1 , \quad (\text{A2})$$

because the strand must also cross above each enclosed ring. The expression for the probability is due to the *one-dimensionality* of strands. The expression yields an *average* number N of microstates at and above the central minimum area given by

$$N = 2 + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{3!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \dots + \frac{1}{n!} + \dots = e = 2.718281828459\dots \quad (\text{A3})$$

and thus yields e microstates per minimum area of a horizon. As a consequence, taking the natural logarithm, Bekenstein's expression for black hole entropy is recovered:

$$\frac{S}{A} = \frac{kc^3}{4G\hbar} \quad (\text{A4})$$

Further exploration also yields the logarithmic correction to the entropy [48, 49]. The value of black hole entropy cannot be confirmed in experiments; however, it is consistent with two further, measurable aspects of black hole thermodynamics.

Because the horizon weave is *tight*, its crossing switches *propagate* from one crossing to the next across the whole horizon surface. During the time T needed to circumnavigate a spherical, non-rotating Schwarzschild horizon of area $A = 4\pi R^2$ at the speed of light,

all crossings of the horizon switch. The horizon energy E is the number N_{cs} of crossing switches per time, multiplied by \hbar :

$$E = \frac{N_{\text{cs}}\hbar}{T} = \frac{A/(4G/c^3)}{2\pi R/c} = \frac{c^4}{2G} R . \quad (\text{A5})$$

Strands thus reproduce the usual relation between the radius and the energy – or the mass – of a Schwarzschild black hole, which experiments confirm [79]. Because of the two-dimensional woven strand configuration, for a distant observer at rest, the mass of the black hole is distributed over the horizon [80] and is *not* concentrated at the center, as is often stated. In this way, strands also explain the maximum angular momentum limit for black holes.

In black holes, the temperature is $T = E/2S$, i.e., half the energy-to-entropy ratio [81]. Using the surface gravitational acceleration $a = GM/R^2 = c^2/2R$, this yields

$$T = \frac{\hbar c}{4\pi k} \frac{1}{R} = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi k c} a . \quad (\text{A6})$$

In total, as expected from the construction, strands *confirm* all of black hole thermodynamics [48–51]. Though various derivations of black hole thermodynamics are available, the strand derivation is particularly simple.

Strands also simplify derivations of further black hole properties. The definition of electric charge from chiral crossings, together with the weave model of black holes, yields the usual *upper limit* for the electric charge of a black hole, because the maximum charge arises if all crossings are chiral. The strand model also confirms that electric charge is *conserved* during the evaporation of a black hole. Figure 2 and the particle tangle classification imply that the only possible *remnants* of black hole evaporation are the known particles. Furthermore, the topological definition of the quantum numbers and the fluctuations of strands in a black hole weave imply that mass – the number of crossings – and angular momentum – the collective rotation of crossings – and electric charge – the topological chirality – are the only macroscopic properties that a black hole can have. Strands thus yield the *no-hair theorem*. Dirac’s trick for a black hole explains why black holes can rotate. Deducing the precise relation between the strand description of black hole rotation and frame dragging, the Lense-Thirring effect, is a nice puzzle. Any observed deviation from these black hole properties would falsify the strand model.

For the case of systems in *flat space*, the fundamental principle with its two configurations implies, from Boltzmann’s expression for entropy, the smallest system entropy $k \ln 2$ and, therefore, as argued in reference [25], the laws of conventional thermodynamics. Strands thus confirm line V of the introduction.

B From strands back to general relativity and quantum gravity

By construction, aggregates of untangled strands yield empty space, curvature, and general relativity. It is interesting to check the conceptual and the experimental consequences of this connection.

First, the fundamental principle implies, by algebraic combination of the quantum of action, of the minimum distance, and of the minimum time, that there is a maximum force $c^4/4G$ and a maximum energy speed c . These two invariant limits imply Einstein’s field equations and the Hilbert Lagrangian, as shown by Gibbons [5] and by others [6–8].

Strands also allow deducing general relativity in other ways. Inhomogeneous aggregates of fluctuating untangled strands of Planck radius lead to spatial curvature. Specifically, average strand shapes yield geodesics. Because all strand configurations follow the principle of least action, and because curvature yields crossing switches, strands imply the Hilbert action and thus Einstein’s field equations [48, 49].

Finally, because strands yield black hole thermodynamics, as shown in references [48–51], strands also imply general relativity. This connection was proven by Jacobson [82] and popularized by Padmanabhan [83, 84] and by Verlinde [85].

All three derivations of general relativity arise in the limit of $\hbar \rightarrow 0$. The limit implies strands of vanishing radius and yields diffeomorphism invariance. The three derivations *exclude* any *measurable* extension or modification to general relativity. Any deviations are predicted to be *unmeasurably small*, confirming the predictions of perturbative relativistic quantum gravity [86, 87]. and the experimental results [3, 9, 88–90], despite collective efforts and incentives to show the contrary. So far, no alternative theory of gravitation that predicts measurable deviations from general relativity has been confirmed, including those of references [91–94].

The minimum measurement errors for area and length prevent the observation of *any* Planck-scale fluctuations of space. Furthermore, in agreement with many investigations [95–101], strands and the Planck limits imply that *single gravitons exist but cannot be detected*. The strand model for gravitons, its properties, and its relation to gravitational mass and to the inverse square law of gravity are explained in Section 5. In total, strands and the minimum measurement errors prevent the observation of any effect of relativistic quantum gravity – apart from the nine lines themselves.

Strands and their fluctuations imply and visualize the equivalence of the entropic description of gravity, of the effective field theoretic description using graviton exchange [102], and of the description with spatial curvature and general covariance. As expected, strands thus *confirm* lines II, III, and V of the introduction, the graviton in line VIII, and the number of dimensions in line IX. In addition, strands confirm the result of Section 2 and Section 4 that no unified *equations* of relativistic quantum gravity are possible; strands extend this result with the prediction that no *new observations* of relativistic quantum gravity are possible. Any contrasting observation would falsify the strand model.

As a note, numerous intensely explored approaches to relativistic quantum gravity are based on filiform constituents that cannot pass through each other, or can be mapped to such constituents [45, 103–112]. These approaches yield three-dimensional physical space but, so far, do not yield the standard model of particle physics with massive neutrinos and all its constants.

C From strands back to spinor wave functions and Dirac’s equation

In 1980, Battey-Pratt and Racey derived the free Dirac equation from tethered motion, i.e., from Dirac’s trick [113]. To complete the derivation of all observations from the fundamental principle, a summary of their work follows, together with further arguments for the uniqueness of the strand model.

Strands and their crossing switches explain and describe the existence of the smallest observable action value: no change smaller than \hbar is observable in nature. The smallest action has many consequences. Angular momentum is defined as action per rotation. The smallest action \hbar divided by the two rotations in the case of fermions yields a spin $\hbar/2$ that

Figure 13 In the strand tangle model, a *spinor wave function*, often modeled with a flag, is the *oriented crossing density* of a fluctuating fermion tangle. The average that defines the oriented crossing density, as everywhere in this article, is taken over all shape fluctuations occurring during a few Planck times. The figure illustrates how strand fluctuations imply a crossing density that yields the wave function with a total central phase (the flag direction). The crossing switch density yields the probability density. The figure is simplified: the local phase of the wave function of a particle depends on the position. The insert illustrates how the geometry of a fluctuating tangle leads to crossings – regions of shortest strand distance – and to an (almost) local density and phase.

is also the smallest possible spin value. The definition of the spin value of an elementary particle with tethers is independent of the mass and rotation speed of the particle, as is observed. Tethers also imply the lack of particles with spin values that are not integer multiples of $\hbar/2$. As a consequence, crossing switches imply that angular momentum is quantized. A literature search found no other ab initio model, in three spatial dimensions, for the quantization of angular momentum.

The crossing switch illustrated in Figure 3 also implies that in nature, crossing numbers have a rounding error of $1/2$. For conjugate observables, this rounding error yields Heisenberg's indeterminacy relation with a minimum error product $\hbar/2$. The crossing switch also visualizes the non-commutativity of nature at the Planck scale. A detailed

investigation, which will be published separately, yields Heisenberg's canonical commutation relation [54, 55]. A literature search found no other *ab initio* model, in three spatial dimensions, for the two relations.

A moving quantum particle with spin has a *rotating* tangle core. If one neglects the minimum length, contracts the oriented tangle core, and recalls that tethers are unobservable, the particle becomes a point with a rotating arrow. This is Feynman's path integral description of quantum particles [26].

But tangles also visualize wave functions. When Dirac explained fermion spin with tethers, his explanation implied that strand tangle *crossings* – the regions of smallest strand distance between two strand segments of a particle tangle – can be used to visualize spinor wave functions.

Definition 6: *Spinor wave functions*, or *Dirac spinors*, are *oriented crossing densities* of a fermion strand tangle.

Equivalently, tangles are fluctuating *skeletons* of wave functions, as illustrated in Figure 13. The geometry of a crossing yields a magnitude and a phase α . Because tangle core rotations yield, via the Dirac trick, crossing switches and quanta of action \hbar , defining a wave function as an oriented crossing density automatically leads to de Broglie's relation. In turn, de Broglie's relation, neglecting spin and relativistic effects, led Schrödinger to his equation. The definition of wave functions as oriented crossing densities also yields superpositions, Hilbert spaces, interference, entanglement, and decoherence, as explained in two upcoming articles. Adding spin implies adding the complete geometry of crossings. The crossing density, the four angles α, β, γ and δ shown in Figure 13, and the three relativistic boost parameters describing length contraction and time dilation (not shown), all taken together, yield the eight real parameters of Dirac spinors.

Once Dirac spinors are defined as oriented crossing densities of tangles, the free Dirac equation can be deduced in three ways. It can be deduced from rotating tethered cores, as done by Battey-Pratt and Racey [113], it can be deduced from the principle of least action together with the fundamental principle, or it can be deduced from the conservation of spin current that is intrinsic to strand tangles. All three deductions will be presented in detail in an upcoming article. As expected, the definition of Dirac spinors as oriented crossing densities – including all angles and the boost effects on the tangle core – yields spin, antiparticles, and all relativistic effects, including virtual particle-antiparticle pairs. As a result, particle tangles arising from untangled vacuum strands model quantum fields excited from the vacuum state [59, 60].

Strands thus *confirm* line IV and line II of the introduction, as expected. With the deduction of the Dirac equation, strands deduce the backbone of the standard model. Any observed deviation from quantum field theory would falsify the strand model and the fundamental principle.

Consistent with the previous results, a literature search found no other *ab initio* derivation, i.e., no Planck-scale derivation from a single principle, of spinor wave functions and of the free Dirac equation. This has several reasons.

1. Apart from Battey-Pratt and Racey's approach [113], several other approaches derive the Dirac equation from an underlying discreteness [114–116]. Other derivations are based on spatial continuity [117–123]. A recent overview of derivations is found in [124]. None of these derivations enables changing continuously from particle to antiparticles and describing interactions, let alone incorporating general relativity.

2. Above all, no alternative constituent and no alternative model in three dimensions

achieves the visualization and the explanation of a particle-independent smallest positive value for spin $\hbar/2$, of rotation behavior, of fermion behavior, and of the spin-statistics theorem. For example, this is not achieved by the book by Duck and Sudarshan [125], nor by the visualizations of pin using the three-dimensional ball B^3 in which opposite points are identified, nor by the coupled pendula presented by Leroy et al. [126, 127], nor by the sphere glowing in different colors constructed by Bernard-Bernardet et al. [128].

3. No topological model other than strands explains, for elementary particles, the appearance of quantum numbers, despite intense explorations [129–143]. In the literature, only the octonion model by Singh also yields unique mass values, mixings, and coupling constants [75–78]. However, it adds further dimensions, particles, and interactions.

4. No other model apart from the strand tangle model explains the quantization of angular momentum and the existence of a smallest action value \hbar – despite numerous efforts [63–68, 70, 144–146].

5. Apart from oriented crossing densities, no other model for wave functions explains particle discreteness and continuous wave functions, despite intense attempts [147–161].

6. At the Planck scale, no description of quantum jumps in atoms differing from Figure 9 is currently available.

7. No Planck-scale model in three dimensions other than strands without ends reproduces the non-commutativity of physical observables.

8. Only the fundamental principle for fluctuating strands explains and visualizes Heisenberg’s indeterminacy relation.

9. No model other than strands explains and visualizes quantum entanglement for *any* number of particles, despite many vigorous attempts [56, 57, 162–174].

10. A literature search did not yield another model describing the countability of photons, their spin \hbar , their boson behavior, their wave behavior, and all their other properties.

11. Only observable crossing switches of unobservable strands appear to eliminate non-contextual hidden variables but to reproduce wave functions, decoherence, and quantum measurements in three dimensions. This unique property of strands will be presented in an upcoming article.

12. A literature search did not yield another model explaining the origin of the principle of least action in quantum theory. It appears that no other model visualizes both \hbar and quantum evolution.

Taken together, these points suggest that there is no alternative to describing quantum theory with fluctuating strands. Any inequivalent alternative description would falsify the strand model and its fundamental principle presented above.

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